

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE ANXIETY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AMONG PAKISTANI STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study aimed at exploring the prospects and underlying resolution of the research. It has discovered the conceivable causes of communication apprehension faced by Pakistani students. The research also aims to explore the approaches opted by the students as well as teachers to tackle the anxiety that they have had while interacting in the Lingua Franca that was obviously English either in the context of Foreign or Second Language. The study was purely qualitative in approach and triangulation technique was applied to gather data for strengthening its findings. The researcher developed a questionnaire comprising 12 open-ended questions to accumulate the elaborated responses of the 200 students and 10 teachers. The purposive technique of data sampling was applied by the researcher while considering the participants of the research. The researcher translated the questionnaire tool of data collection for students in Urdu language for their better understanding and giving appropriate responses. But it was quite convenient and easily intelligible for the teachers in the target language. The data was gathered through oral interviews accompanied by direct and participatory observations for further strengthening the outcomes of the research. It has become a longitudinal descriptive case study consisting of six months. The data collected through triangulation technique was integrated and analyzed for drawing findings and conclusion.

INTRODUCTION

Due to technological advancement, knowledge about the process of language acquisition has improved to a greater extent. Usually, language acquisition is considered to be the outcome of general conversation and interaction amongst the people. Let's take the example of Behaviorists who are of the view that language can be acquired through imitation, association and reinforcement. They also assert that a language may be acquired through Universal Grammar (UG). A few mentionable prominent linguists are Edward Sapir and Benjamin Lee Whorf, Ferdinand de Saussure, Skinner, Pinker and specially Noam Chomsky who are known as the pioneers of biological linguistics and originators of UG.

CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

The Grammar Translation Method (GTM), which has been used to teach English for many years, has proven to be more effective than other teaching techniques. The ability to read and write has been vital in language teaching and has changed the educational system, but

it has not been particularly effective for instructors or students in general. Researchers have always been interested in how grammar has developed in a variety of circumstances where foreign languages are spoken. Different applied linguistics researchers have made an effort to approach the problem from a variety of angles. Teaching grammar, whether overtly or implicitly, has long been a major issue of debate from these views. Numerous grammar-related topics have attracted attention and in-depth study in literature. While others have tended to concentrate on the challenges associated with the acquisition and appropriate use of passive constructions in English by non-native speakers of different first language backgrounds, some have concentrated on tense (Bardovi-Harlig & Reynolds ,1995); (Oshita , 2000); (Willis ,2004)."

However, other researchers have looked into the learning of conditionals (Willis, 2004) and the challenges faced by language learners in foreign-language environments.

English Existential Constructions (ECs) are among them and have also been a significant research focus, offering the greatest challenges for speakers of languages where such structures are absent or are simply different from those of English (see section 2, Theoretical Framework below). The ECs (Biber, 1999) have always been a cause of difficulty for Urdu learners of English, which is relevant to the study's objectives. This was noticed realistically by numerous teaching practitioners in classroom settings. Learners frequently avoid these structures or choose to use other structures that may be completely inappropriate or even unrelated to the grammatical requirements of a specific linguistic and communicative context, despite having received a thorough teaching of these structures and having been informed about their specific use and function.

The methods and approaches used to teach these grammatical features, however, could also be ineffective. According to Atai, Gheitanchian, (2009) and Nazari (2011), "most Professors in

Pakistan, especially at undergraduate level (English has been taught since first grade at school level in Pakistan), prefer a traditional Presentation-Practice-Production (P-P-P) Model of instruction for ECs in classroom settings and do not give learners tasks that would improve their capability in and mastery of such elements in real communicative instances." To enable better acquisition and more fluent and appropriate use of such grammatical characteristics in a foreign language setting, perhaps more narrowly-focused Focus on Form (F on F) assignments are necessary.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The primary emphasis of this research is to study the effects of communicative apprehension during the process of acquisition of the Target Language, English. Particularly, the researcher aims at exploring the various elements mounting the communicative anxiety amongst students which impedes their capability of acquiring the target language, English.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1.To examine the factors that contribute to communicative anxiety during teaching learning process.
- 2.To find out the repercussions of communicative anxiety in the acquisition/Learning of TL (English Language).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1.What significant factors do contribute in developing communicative anxiety amongst undergraduate students?
- 2.How does communicative anxiety hinder the process of acquisition of TL amongst BS level students?

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The researchers had thoroughly gone through the effective filter hypothesis of Dr. Krashen (1982) in the context of second language acquisition/learning. They had applied and explored the effects of communicative anxiety on the acquisition of English language.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

It is quite obvious viewpoint and supported by the research studies of many renowned scholars cum linguists like Noam Chomsky as well as Dr.

Stephen Krashen and the rest that apprehension is amongst one of barriers in the progression of acquisition of target linguistic repertoire. But in the current study the researcher has explored particularly the effect of Communicative anxiety on the acquisition of TL in a classroom environment of teaching learning process along with findings with appropriate remedy as well. The study highlights the numerous factors causing communicative anxiety consequently influencing and impeding the process of proficiency of TL acquisition/learning. It has also proved a torchbearer for the future researchers to further explore its merits and demerits by replicating and reaffirming its results in their own territories and settings. It has not only highlighted the severity of problem rather offers an appropriate remedy for the issue.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study deals with the effects of communicative anxiety on the process of acquisition/learning of English Language in the classroom settings at undergraduate level. It does not consider

the various other biological and the rest of factors causing anxiety and its repercussions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher has conducted this research in an appropriate and systematic manner for exploring the crucial factors causing hindrances in the acquisition of TL (English Language). For the purpose of gathering qualitative data, many different tools have been employed. Both a questionnaire to assess communicative anxiety and a thorough background questionnaire have been completed by participants. Furthermore, direct as well as participatory observations and oral interviews have also been conducted to further strengthen the study and to get the crystal clear picture of the problem as well as its solution findings. This study used a literature review and conceptual modeling as its main research methods.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The researchers have taken filled questionnaire from undergraduate students of public sector University at Chakwal. The primary focus was on the language acquisition/learning process

amongst the students. It was an oral as well as written evaluation including observations, interviews and getting feedback on the qualitative questionnaires both from students as well as their respective English Language Teachers. For this study, the researcher has ensured the participation of teachers as well students of BS-classes drawn from Public Sector University in Chakwal. It has been a qualitative research comprises initially of 200 students and 10 teachers from semester 1st, 3rd, 5th and 7th. Finally, after seeking the willingness of the participants, the sample size was reduced to 60 students and 4 professors. The rationale of keeping the sample size minimum was to make it a longitudinal case study of six months of ESL/EFL undergraduates' classes, to observe classroom teaching learning and handle the qualitative data appropriately. The qualitative study's goal is to investigate the variables that contribute to anxiety when speaking English as a second or foreign language. An open-ended questionnaire was employed by the researchers to gather information from

the individuals. (Undergraduate-Students and Professors) that belonged to public sector University of District Chakwal. Moreover, to further strengthen the findings and removes various loopholes and deficiencies, the researcher has applied triangulation technique by including an Oral Interview as well as direct and participatory observations tools for data collection as well.

DATA COLLECTION TOOLS AND PROCEDURES

Firstly, the participants were asked to fill out a permission form before the researcher asked them to contribute to the study, which is how the researchers first gathered the data. After that, the contributors filled out a demographic form that asked those questions about their gender, age, and other details. After that, the participants were asked to respond to a 12-questions open-ended survey about factors affecting speaking anxiety in a classroom where English was the dominant language. Similar to that, the next questions focused on how they handled their nervousness while

speaking English as a second language in a classroom where the majority of the students spoke the language. Secondly, the researchers have very keenly observed the classes of these participants of the study and gathered data through direct and participatory observations. Thirdly, the researchers have thoroughly conducted the interviews of the participants orally and collected pertinent data for strengthening the repertoire of this study.

DATA ANALYSIS TRIANGULATION TECHNIQUE

Finally, the researchers have applied triangulation technique of data analysis and profoundly analyzed by adopting collective case studies to draw final conclusions and recommendations.

THE SAMPLE AND SAMPLING PROCESS

Using the purposive sampling approach, a sample for the study was selected from the Public Sector University in the district Chakwal. Sixty students from various semesters provided the data, which was gathered. These 60 pupils were split equally between boys and girls,

with 30 being each. Randomly chosen from the 1st, 3rd, 5th and 7th semesters of BS English classes, these participants in the study completed two different qualitative questionnaires (written and oral), each asking about the factors that contribute to ESL/EFL speaking anxiety and the coping mechanisms used by the students to manage it. The questionnaire items were also translated by the researchers into the Urdu language to guarantee that the questions were understood. The specialists checked the translations, and they also included any proposed edits. In addition the third data sampling and gathering technique of direct and participatory observations was also employed by the researchers to further ensure the quality and authenticity of the data for better analysis and findings as well.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

QUALITATIVE QUESTIONNAIRE ANALYSIS

FACTORS EFFECTING EFL /ESL COMMUNICATING ANXIETY

The contributors of the study provided with variable replies to the questionnaire regarding the most credible factors of EFL / ESL Speech Anxiety.

LACKING SELF-CONFIDENCE

The analysis of the responses pointed to "loss of confidence" as one of the key themes. It was the most often mentioned response, and 45 of the 60 responses among the 60 that were recorded concluded that it was a major contributing factor to EFL/ESL speech anxiety. The majority of the contributors also agreed, albeit not in exactly the same words, with the responses that indicated a lack of confidence as the primary cause of EFL / ESL speaking anxiety. A handful of the responses exactly matched the words "Less confident," "Lack of confidence," or "Low confidence," indicating that students lack confidence. Following the same pattern, a few of the

succinct comments also allude to a "loss of confidence" when speaking in English as a "foreign language" in particular contexts. "Lack of confidence is also the key issue," "Lack of confidence when speaking English," and "Lack of confidence is the main thing that makes me anxious" are all expressions used to describe the core issues with me. More details were provided in a few of the responses that were given. One of the main reasons I'm afraid to talk in English in a school where everyone speaks English is the absence of self-confidence.

IMPACT OF VOCABULARY

The next notion that dominated the responses turns out to be of "vocabulary". It was indicated as the second most common source of EFL/ESL speech anxiety in 42 of the 60 responses. Some of the responses in this cluster were also succinct and exact in nature as they made references to vocabulary, such as "Vocabulary, Hard Words," "Vocabulary is the Major Factor," and "Lack of Vocabulary," which show that they are in line with the topic of vocabulary. The participants also listed difficulty with

word pronunciation as an issue. Additionally, it was planned for this to be connected to a lack of vocabulary. This classification also included some phrases as responses, which also provided a hint about vocabulary. "My vocabulary is not very strong," "I also have a limited vocabulary," and "my limited vocabulary caused me anxiety when speaking English." Comparatively speaking, several of the comments were more specific. The lack of vocabulary, in my opinion, is the most problematic aspect of an English-speaking lesson. This is also the main cause of my fear that others will make fun of me if I make a mistake in speaking. Vocabulary issues are to blame for this.

EMBARRASSMENT AND RIDICULE-RELATED PHOBIAS

40 participants supported the third most significant item, "Embarrassment and ridicule-related phobias," which was virtually leachable with the second factor. Many of the contributors used the expressions "I am afraid of being mocked," "Other students may laugh at me," "If someone makes fun of or

laughs," "Afraid that other students will laugh at me," "Afraid that masses will make fun of me," "I may utter something incorrect that individuals will make me a laughing stalk" "Reluctance for getting embarrassed in front of everyone," "I am scared that if I make a mistake others will laugh at me," and "...can "The major factors in an English language speaking lecture room that cause me apprehensive is fear phobias...if I would say a single word of anything so making fun of that word in class" which supports that the members had a fear of being ridiculed or humiliated.

PEER STRESS AND HOSTILE AUDIENCE

The authors of the research highlighted peer pressure as the fourth factor that contributed to communication anxiety. This differed from the previous groups in that it dealt with the presence of the students who displayed snobbish behaviour and demoralized other learners by their actions, as opposed to the caustic behaviour encountered by the students struggling with EFL/ESL communication anxiety. Because they

did not feel comfortable around their classmates, 39 of the contributors admitted to having communication anxiety related to their EFL or ESL. Despite this, they did not act in a disrespectful manner toward their classmates. Many of the responses were short and to the point. The responses were "Hostile audience," "All other pupils," and "...demotivation from the crowd." The majority of responses include words and phrases like "Also, the environment is not so conducive," "Students...made me nervous while speaking English," "Sometimes when audience is not collaborating makes me anxious," "Presence of Postgraduate-level student with his complacent face that he knows all," and "...when I come to speak English - I all the while thinks that what the other can think about my English." Additional replies included descriptions and were labeled as "Disturbance and bantering of those students who are extremely proficient in speaking English..." and "One of the important variables in an English language speaking

classroom is the approach of the Professor and the audience."

FACING A LOT OF FOLKS

The fifth most shared inference gotten from the outcomes was the fear of facing a multitude. 37 contributors from the 60 who responded were not of feeling at ease while communicating in the target language facing a crowd. Some of the responses to the query were direct in nature. These included phrases like "People crowd," "The crowd, Stage fright," and "The addressees make us nervous." However, the majority of the responses were of an all-inclusive nature, such as "People sitting around me make me feeling anxious," "The main is that people are looking and listening to me," "The very first thing which typically makes me anxious is to face the audience," "The major factor that makes me anxious of speaking English in the classroom include the stress that is given to me when everyone's eyes are focused on me," and "Factor that makes me anxious of speaking English in the classroom is the staring and gazing of my fellows.

GRAMMATICAL INTRICACIES

In addition to the responses to the open-ended questions, there were reports of Pakistani EFL/ESL students dealing with difficulties that were seen as serious barriers to learning English as ESL around the world. Thirty Six of the participants acknowledged that they were not adept in using grammar rules and believed that grammatical complexities were the main source of their worry in EFL/ESL communication. Specific phrases like "Lack of grammar skills," "Grammatical errors," "Grammatical mistakes," and "...grammatical problems" were used in several of the responses. Language used in some of the responses included the phrases "Grammatical blunders while speaking English," "...and to recall the correct usage of tense while speaking," and "I believe that my grammar and tenses are not that much strong." Many of the responses were brief explanations, such as "The rules of grammar are the main cause of anxiety during speaking English," "Sometimes grammatical mistakes, the fright arises to utter a correct tense, without slipping of

the tongue," "Mostly I make grammatical errors so whenever I speak becomes anxious that whether my words or grammar are accurate or not," and "In my opinion, some major factors in an English language speaking classroom,"

DEFICIENCY IN MAKING PROPER PREPARATION

After acknowledging the consequences of EFL/ESL communication anxiety, "lack of preparation" was identified as the next most prevalent response. Lack of preparation was mentioned by 35 out of the 60 participants as a contributing cause to communication anxiety in EFL/ESL. Some of the participants were brief in their comments, using phrases like "Not knowing what to say" and "limited information about the things." Others, on the other hand, used one-liners to express their opinions, such as "Feels awkward when speak English that is not prepared" and "Not knowing what to say further if not prepared." There were not many thorough responses. "I hesitate a lot when I'm asked to talk on a subject I don't know much about," "The teacher asked a question, but I didn't

prepare beforehand..." I need to think before I speak.

ANXIETY OVER MAKING MISTAKES

A contributing component to ESL/EFL communication anxiety was "fear over making mistakes." 34 of the 60 participants in the study agreed that the contributors to the study suffered from EFL/ESL speech anxiety as a result of being discouraged by the thought of making mistakes. Some of the answers were phrasal and emotive in nature, such as "...error fright," "Fearful to commit an error in front of everyone," and "I am terrified of making mistakes while I was conversing in English." Some of the responses were more detailed and included clarifications, such as "Secondarily, if I made a mistake during a communication or presentation and someone fixed it during my speech is a most horrible thing because it can cause more mistakes," and "The only thing which will make me restless will be if I make a mistake and couldn't tackle (tackle) it couldn't overcome it."

ADVERSE AND HARSH ATTITUDE REFLECTED BY TEACHER

The major problem confronted by pupils in EFL / ESL teaching-learning classrooms atmosphere is of negative approach exhibited by the teacher. In the study at hand, 33 answers in particular mentioned this as a source of anxiety. These responses included "Teacher's focus on me," "The questions of teacher," "...teacher...made me apprehensive while speaking English," "Whether the teacher would insult me if I use inappropriate English," "The major factors in an English-speaking classroom that make me anxious of speaking English in the classroom is...critical feedback," and "One of the major factors in an English-speaking classroom is the attitude of the teacher and the observers." Anxiety would result from a negative attitude from them.

PROBLEM OF DEBILITATING FLUENCY

According to responses on the aforementioned questionnaire, "Lack of Fluency" was cited as another issue contributing to EFL/ESL

communication anxiety by 32 out of 60 participants. The participants said things like "my accent," "not good in English," "communication power is not that much good," "not everyone grasp the way I explain," and "I found some problems because I think I am not very good in speaking English."

LACK OF COMPREHENSION

The next salient factor impacting EFL / ESL communication anxiety documented from amongst the responses of the unobstructed questionnaire is Only 31 out of 60 participants gave a specific response to the phrase "Comprehension Problem"; these responses included "Less understanding," "Fluency, the flow of words," and "Fast speed of instructors while asking questions."

COMPARING YOURSELF TO OTHER STUDENTS

The "Comparing Yourself to Other Students" led by the EFL/ESL students themselves was cited as a contributing cause to EFL/ESL communication anxiety by 31 of the 60 contributors. The students take great pride in other

students' success and are deeply invested in it. Due of this, ugly rivalry or resentful feelings frequently erupted. Participants said things like, "I feel degraded when my friend speaks good English then (than) me," "Other major factor is that a lot of people speak well than me, so I become more mindful," and "In my opinion, if we are sitting in the class along with other students attending the class, so lacking of confidence occur in myself due to the fact that I can't speak English properly or correctly rather than those students who speak English more fluently."

FEAR OF UNDESIRABLE ASSESSMENT

Out of the 60 respondents, only 30 participants expressed concern about receiving poor ratings. The response was, "Only when there are low grades on the line; otherwise, I never get nervous about speaking English in class. My confidence is shaken and communication is hampered if the teacher awards me low marks. I'm very discouraged by unfair outcomes.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SUMMARY

In order to examine the key elements of EFL/ESL Communication anxiety, the instructors who contributed to the discussion were requested to share their thoughts. The study's findings caused a reevaluation of these major contributing elements that affect students at undergraduate-level by mounting their communication anxiety when they tend to communicate in EFL or ESL. According to the findings, one of the main causes of EFL/ESL communication anxiety amongst undergraduate students at Public sector University is their lower self-confidence. Many students identified the main cause of their low confidence as having crippled fluency in the target language in their responses. Additionally, they acknowledged and agreed with the researcher that their lack of prior exposure to EFL/ESL communication, particularly in the beginning of their academic careers, had a negative impact in this area. Another significant factor that has increased its

visibility among students is their fear of speaking in front of large crowds, which can be attributed, once again, to the lack of exposure and opportunities for EFL/ESL presenters to communicate in front of large audiences during the early stages of their academic careers. When students encounter huge crowds, they experience fear and burden that make them hesitant and reluctant to speak in the target language. This is also one of the main causes of communication anxiety in EFL and ESL. According to the replies provided by study participants, peer pressure is another cause of EFL / ESL communication anxiety. As EFL/ESL students try to gauge their progress and skill in contrast to their colleagues, it has been noticed that they frequently find themselves lacking. This may be an indication of resentment toward their own abilities and anger toward EFL/ESL communication abilities. Anxiety related to EFL/ESL communication is also thought to be influenced by presenters' fear of being humiliated at the hands of their peers. Since it might easily prevent the students

from learning EFL/ESL, this may be the most discouraging and, hence, the most serious of all the causes of public speech fear, the highest. Another issue that EFL and ESL speakers encounter in their ESL and EFL speaking exercises and tests is the distribution of marks and the terror of earning low grades. One of the main causes of ESL/EFL communication anxiety among students is the fear of making mistakes when taking ESL/EFL speaking exams or participating in ESL/EFL speaking activities. The worry is a common reaction in the absence of adequate preparation and may result from a lack of practice before an EFL/ESL communication activity or EFL/ESL speaking test. By changing the way the Professors instruct, it is possible to considerably measure the anxiety that emerges from the dread of making mistakes and the worry of earning poor marks in EFL/ESL communication activities and speaking tests.

One of the main causes of EFL/ESL communication anxiety is inadequate grammar and partial vocabulary proficiency. The direct

interpretation method, in which students translate what they want to say from their native tongue into the preferred language, in this case English, has become a common practice among EFL and ESL students. Their slow speech, which is interspersed with gaps, some of which are longer than others, makes the strategy clear. English has a large vocabulary because it has borrowed many terms from other languages all around the world. This is a significant challenge to undergraduate EFL/ESL students as they struggle to find the perfect term to utilize in a given circumstance.

DISCUSSION

The participants of the various groups, who had differing degrees of English language competency, seemed to be self-regulating of the impact that anxiety had on learning English as a foreign language. The students were believed to rely more on contributing motivation than integrative drive to master a language (Lian & Budin, 2014). "The results also indicated that a high level of anxiety was linked to English language classes as opposed to English use and tests, where

they reported much less anxiety. A very obviously favorable association between L1 and ESL/EFL linguistics skills was found, as is evident from the study done by Abu-Rabia and Shakkour (2014). However, research showed a negative correlation between language proficiency in both English and Hebrew and language anxiety. The contributors approach both languages with a similar level of anxiety. The results of this study demonstrated the role neuroticism, among other personality types, had in the assessment of the likelihood of language anxiety and success in EFL/ESL. The research (Gopang, 2015) on the topic of English language communication anxiety that the students of Lasbela University encountered indicated speaking apprehension and terror of negative evaluation as being among the main findings. In a separate study by Gopang, Bughio, and Pathan, (2015) that examined the stages of apprehension associated with learning a foreign language in English-speaking students attending public sector institutions, the findings showed that

undergraduate students at Lasbela University shared a common level of speaking anxiety both inside and outside of the classroom. The pupils avoid situations that might require them to use English since they are hesitant to participate in them. When they speak with native narrators, the anxiousness is more obvious. (Dar & Khan, 2014) noted a similar pattern in the anxiety levels among engineering students, which they attributed to apprehension about spoken communication.

Similar findings to the ones in the present study were obtained from research on the same topic done in Pakistan. Speaking in front of others is the main source of anxiety, closely followed by concerns over grammatical errors, according to Awan et al (2010) 's study on EFL classroom anxiety and the impact it had on the students' results. One of the main causes of speech anxiety, according to a different study conducted by Adeel (2011) and Hussain et al. (2020) on the topic of anxiety in Graduation Apprentices of English as a Foreign Language in the Pakistani context, was

self-constructed imprints and ideas of the EFL/ESL presenters about their own competences. The classrooms' overly strict and conservative atmosphere contributed to the anxiousness. In their study on anxiety among students of English as a second language, Waseem and Jibeen (2013) found that "conditional or instrumental motivation was recognized to be a substantial cause of second language learning anxiety. This included anxiety over receiving poor grades, a dread of speaking, worry about tests, and a sense of stress related to English studies. On the other hand, integrative motivation did nothing but exacerbate the anxiety brought on by the worry of receiving poor feedback. Similar findings were found in a study conducted by Nazir et al. (2014) on the topic of second language communication anxiety in Pakistani EFL/ESL students at the intermediate level. The findings suggested communiqué anxiety and fear of public speaking.

According to Shahzadi and Zahabia (2014) in a study on the difficulties related to English language

proficiency state that students at the University of Sargodha experienced, the participants felt more at ease speaking in their native tongue and showed hesitation while using English as a foreign language. One of the contributing elements to ESL/EFL communication anxiety is this unsure behaviour, which is treatable by making adjustments to the educational methods used. According to Sheikh and Hussain (2014), another important fundamental cause of anxiety is the pressure parents place on their children to achieve the remaining marks necessary for admission to a tertiary institution. This refers to the escalating fear of failure among students, which can result in poor marks and average performance in in-class communication tasks. In their study on the relationship between students' anxiety and their conduct, Zahid and Ghani (2014) identified the students' actions as an indicator of anxiety. The research's conclusions indicated that the students' behaviour was in response to their anxiety levels. As the student considers learning English as a foreign

language to be easier and has fewer levels of communication anxiety, a productive approach with an expectant outlook on the procedure taken by the student shows optimistic results.

The anxiety levels of students learning a new language may rise due to a variety of other factors present in the classroom. Another study (Yahya, 2013) identified test anxiety as having the lowest mean, while speech anxiety (2.80) and fear of unfavorable evaluation had the highest means (2.93, 2.90, and 2.93, respectively). To reduce the impact of trait anxiety (TA) on communication anxiety, it was suggested that ELTs accompany them into the classrooms and establish a positive and energetic atmosphere. Learning anxiety can be considerably reduced by a supportive environment and positive moods. Given how demanding the role of mentoring is, it should be clear to the mentors that they are doing so. The type of difficulties and worry that students face when they learn a foreign language must be understood in order to effectively support them. The mentor can create a practical lesson plan

that meets the needs of the students' experiencing communication anxiety with the help of this appreciation. Language classrooms have occasionally been transformed into language laboratories, with the teachers acting as the researchers.

The teachers must seize this opportunity to identify the language-related issues that students are facing and act as detectives to find solutions. The instructor needs to be knowledgeable about the abilities of their students, their attitudes about the language, the motivations underlying their unbiased responses to language learning activities, and the factors affecting their productivity in the classroom. Not only would making these decisions benefit the students by ensuring better results by fostering the quality of their language acquisition, boosting their morale, and reducing the factors underlying the anxiety, but it would also be advantageous for the instructor by assisting them in bringing improvement to their professional proficiencies. "A supportive and laid-back style of the

instructor can play a big impact in decreasing the anxiety levels of the students," claims (Young ,1999). Less restrictive teaching techniques, such as maintaining a stress-free environment in the classroom, developing a rapport with the students, using humor, and offering support to students, can inspire learners to be more confident and reduce their foreign language anxiety, which will help the learning process

FINDINGS

Numerous findings have been made as a result of research on the variables contributing to the stress that EFL/ESL presenters feel while learning and using English as a foreign language. The study emphasized the significance of the role played by the teachers and the measures they take to relieve stress from their students in order to lessen anxiety among the students in their study into the role played by factors like anxiety, demonstrated behavior, and morale of the pupils as they acquire English at undergraduate level in Pakistan.

This further supports the notion that, in particular situations, the presence of the

opposing gender can cause speech anxiety. It was found out that female students reported feeling more stressed and anxious than their male counterparts. While the male students tended to shy away from unexpected events, the female students still exhibited apprehensive behaviour while planning ahead for Communication activities. The tendency of female students to withhold accurate information out of fear of having to face punishments in public was another pattern that emerged. Thus, the female students' reluctance to actively participate in events was partly due to their concern of receiving a poor grade. In this regard, the male students had a different mindset and were perceived as less fearful of social embarrassment. Competition among female students, particularly with those performing much better, lowers their self-esteem and eventually causes anxiety in the students. The anxiety levels of the female students appeared to be influenced by how people perceive their progress when they use English. One element that was found to be common to both the male and female

EFL/ESL students was their misperceptions of their own communication abilities in English, the target language. The principal factors of causing communication anxiety were the shaking confidence, poor vocabulary, constant fear and feelings of being become a laughingstock, Pressure of peers, failure of facing the masses, grammatical intricacies, inappropriate curriculum, rude and discouraging response of the teacher, lack of motivation, debilitating self-esteem, high effective filter, partially developed monitor, lack of reading and listening habits, non-availability of proper A/V aids and scarcity of comprehensible input. The researcher had figured out through triangulation technique the strategies of fixing and coping up with the issue of debilitating anxiety regarding the target language (TL) teaching-learning particularly communicating competence and performance of the learners.

CONCLUSION

This study is significant in several respects despite focusing on a small

number of variables. It has focused on young undergraduate students like most of the studies on language anxiety have been conducted in professional and academic settings. Through a comparison of undergraduate level pupils and their teachers, this study broadens the scope of existing research on anxiety. The results of this study show how communicative anxiety and language learning are related in Pakistani circumstances where language proficiency is more important. The link between them and anxiety has to be explored more because students in nations like ours lose out on numerous possibilities because they don't practice using their goal language proficiency. When learning is the goal, emphasis on the content, on the practical pursuits of students' interests, and on successes is typically given priority by professors and students. Intellectual participation among students who are having trouble concentrating on their academic work may stop. Instead of allowing students to pursue their conceptual improvement while believing that the specific language

skills will naturally develop alongside the concepts, we should think about ways to encourage students' intellectual involvements and analysis, including but not limited to educational experiences and academic investigation.

The researchers came to the following conclusion after the above-mentioned extensive discussion; the results of the data collected reveal that the EFL/ESL students of the Public sector University in district Chakwal suffer a moderate level of general EFL/ESL communication anxiety. When using English as a second language for communication purposes, EFL/ESL speakers continue to perceive a certain amount of ambiguity and encounter subject-specific difficulties. Their confidence, as well as the acquisition process and capabilities, are negatively impacted by the increased degrees of anxiousness. However, it is also proven that intense EFL / ESL communication anxiety results from peer pressure. However, associates can also serve as supportive material in reducing the stress of EFL/ESL speakers. The EFL/ESL

speakers compare their growth to that of their peers who also speak EFL/ESL and become anxious when they outperform them, which adds to the uncomfortable feeling of competition.

EFL/ESL speakers from undergraduate level public sector University have reported experiencing high levels of anxiety due to their fear of receiving a poor grade; both students and Professors worry much about the grades they might receive for the EFL/ESL speaking tasks included in assessments. Their worry about EFL/ESL speaking tests is increased by their experiences of passing the tests. The presenters may experience tremendous levels of stress and worry before the EFL/ESL speaking test, yet they feel at ease while taking it. As indicated by the EFL/ESL speakers, trying to understand the instructor's instructions is another component that could help to alleviate nervousness. While many EFL/ESL speakers are said to find this to be a source of learning anxiety, many students do not find it to be an issue.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- To expand the range and scope of the current study, it is advised to conduct a thorough, all-encompassing investigation to learn more about the numerous additional causes of EFL/ESL communication anxiety in the Pakistani context related to diverse territorial situations.
- More thorough studies covering a wider range of topics should start in order to see if there are any additional elements that may be taken into account in order to better understand and master the target language.
- Future research on communicative anxiety should take into account the fact that there are considerable disparities between the two gender groups. The result supports earlier studies by showing that communicative anxiety is related to proficiency and more specifically to studies on anxiety and multilingualism.

- The most important thing to remember is that it is beneficial for educators, curriculum developers, and teachers to plan and modify their instructional strategies and learning materials in order to make the process of FL acquisition more thorough and effective while minimizing the influence of communicative anxiety.

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APPENDIX A

(1):-Qualitative Questionnaire on “Exploring the Role of Communicative Anxiety in English Language Acquisition Among Pakistani Students”

1:- How does confidence contribute in coping up with the communicative anxiety?

2:-What is the impact of vocabulary on communication in the context of speech anxiety?

3:- How does fear of humiliation and being ridiculed hinder the process of communication? 4:-Is there any impact of peer pressure and hostile behavior of the audience on speaker that causes speech anxiety?

5:-How do you feel while facing a lot of folks during communication?

6:- Do you think grammar plays a pivotal role in communication and reducing speech anxiety? 7:-How does proper preparation of the content affect your delivery of speech and manage your speech anxiety?

8:-Do you feel fear of committing mistakes while communicating in the “Target Language”? 9:- How do Professors’ mentoring and proper responses help you out in dealing with speech anxiety?

10:- Do you experience the problem of debilitating fluency and accuracy during communication? 11:-Do you suffer difficulty in understanding and lack of comprehension in the “Target Language”?

12:- How often do you make your comparison with the other pupils in communication?